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In the Service of the Eastern Bloc: Czechoslovak Intelligence and the Cyprus Conflict 1974–1989

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ABSTRACT

Even after the division of the island in 1974, the ‘Cyprus Issue’ remained a significant determinant in the relations between Greece and Turkey. In the context of the ongoing Cold War, the Eastern Bloc sought to exploit this situation, aiming to undermine the cohesion of NATO’s southeastern wing. The primary objective of this study is to assess how one of the socialist states, Czechoslovakia, attempted to influence the Cyprus conflict between 1974 and 1989 through its foreign intelligence services. The study illustrates this through the example of the Czechoslovak residency in Nicosia, showcasing Czechoslovakia’s intelligence methods in recruiting foreign collaborators, acquiring information, and conducting intelligence operations in one of the world’s most geopolitically exposed regions.

Introduction

On Sunday, 20 September 1981, a married couple of Cypriot nationality arrived at the main railway station in Prague via a regular train service from Vienna. They entered on non-passport visas to avoid leaving any trace of their presence in Czechoslovakia. The two visitors had a busy programme organized by the Czechoslovak Ministry of the Interior over the next three days. While the wife was given a tour of Prague, Jablonec in North Bohemia or the Konopiště castle, her husband spent most of his time negotiating with Czechoslovak intelligence officials. On one of the working lunches, attended by prominent guests, including the Deputy Minister of the Interior or the Chief of Czechoslovak Intelligence, he was awarded the ‘Medal of the National Security Corps’. The man honoured was Pavlos Stokkos, the deputy head of the Cyprus police, who had been collaborating with Czechoslovak spy station (residency) in Nicosia since 1978 as an agent of the Czechoslovak secret police under the codename BELIS.¹ The course of the September trip of Stokkos and his wife to Prague, who were to be on holiday in Austria at that time, shows how the Czechoslovak foreign intelligence (the First Directorate of the National Security Corps) valued its agent. However, his award was also to a large extent a recognition of the work of the residency in Nicosia, which soon after its establishment in 1976 became one of the most successful Czechoslovak spy stations abroad.

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The modern history of Cyprus is intrinsically linked to the work of secret services. The attention of the authors was drawn to the activities of British intelligence during the efforts of the National Organisation of Cypriot Fighters (EOKA) to end British rule over the island and annex it to Greece in the second half of the 1950s.² Others have focused on Cyprus as a valuable territory used by the United Kingdom and the United States for signals intelligence.³ Much has also been written about the efforts of Western intelligence agencies to interfere in the affairs of the Republic of Cyprus, or the attempts to overthrow President Makarios, particularly during the events of 1964 and 1974.⁴ Some studies have also already approached the activities of the Greek or Turkish secret services and their efforts to influence the development of the 'Cyprus Issue'.⁵

However, what is still not sufficiently mapped are the activities of Eastern European intelligence services on the island even though the Eastern Bloc countries actively intervened in the development of the 'Cyprus Issue' during the Cold War.⁶ Socialist states long supported the independence of the Republic of Cyprus, opposed its membership in NATO, sought to remove British bases, and used the Greek-Turkish dispute over Cyprus to weaken Western unity.⁷ In pursuing this strategy, they also utilized their secret services. The Czechoslovak Socialist Republic (ČSSR) became one of the close allies of the newly formed Republic of Cyprus. It maintained close political and economic relations with the Cypriot government and sympathized with its non-aligned policy. Moreover, since the 1950s, the Communist Party of Czechoslovakia (KSČ) has maintained contact with the Progressive Party of the Working People (AKEL). Czechoslovakia's supportive stance towards Cyprus was evident through the arms imports in 1966 and 1972, as well as previously undisclosed deliveries before the 1974 coup.⁸ Czechoslovak intelligence had been active on the island since the early 1960s. Cyprus offered an intriguing operational theatre with the potential to gather valuable information concerning events in the Eastern Mediterranean and the Middle East. Leveraging the close ties between Czechoslovakia and Cyprus, established as early as the 1960s, Czechoslovak intelligence gradually developed a network of collaborators and informants, especially after 1976 when residency in Nicosia was established.

Building on previous research,⁹ the aim of this study is to assess how Czechoslovak secret services attempted to influence the political situation in Cyprus and intervened into Cyprus conflict between 1974 and 1989. Another goal of the study is to demonstrate, using the example of the Nicosia residency, the methods employed by Czechoslovak intelligence in recruiting collaborators, obtaining information, and conducting intelligence operations and psychological warfare in Cyprus. The paper examines the activities of Czechoslovak intelligence in Cyprus from the three interconnected perspectives: 1) the intelligence landscape on the island—in the broader context of the international situation at the time, this perspective will examine the objectives of Czechoslovak intelligence in Cyprus, the conditions that intelligence had for its work as well as cooperation with other Eastern Bloc intelligence services; 2) network of clandestine collaborators will analyse in more detail the methods by which the Czechoslovak secret services recruited Cypriot nationals to cooperate, what their motives were and what type of information they passed on; 3) the last level will focus on specific Czechoslovak intelligence operations in Cyprus.

The study heavily relies on documents from the former Czechoslovak Ministry of Interior, which are now accessible to researchers at the Archive of Security Services in Prague (ABS). Specifically, these are the surviving parts of the Cyprus residency file and

the personal files of collaborators. Although these documents constitute some of the most classified possessions of the secret services, the Czech Republic, as part of the process of coming to terms with its past, has chosen to declassify them to unveil the history of communist Czechoslovakia in all its complexity. Such detailed and previously highly classified documents in such breadth have not been declassified by any Western secret services, not even Russia. Exceptions in this respect are Poland and the former German Democratic Republic, which have also declassified a significant part of similar documentation.¹⁰ Complemented by archival materials from the Czech National Archive (NA) and the Archive of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (AMZV), this paper delves not only into the debates concerning the evolution of the Cyprus conflict after 1974 but also contributes to a deeper comprehension of the dynamics of the Cold War and reinterprets the relationships between the Eastern Bloc and the non-aligned states. This approach, which leverages recently declassified archival materials from former communist countries to challenge previous research predominantly based on Western sources, is termed the 'New Cold War History'.¹¹

Intelligence landscape

Czechoslovakia established diplomatic relations with the Republic of Cyprus shortly after its independence, but no embassy was opened on the island until 1964. As permanent intelligence officers could not be legalized by the embassy under these circumstances, the responsibility for the island fell on the residency in Athens. Its staff only commuted to Cyprus on a regular basis.¹² This situation persisted until 1970, when Josef Grégr was appointed as the new Czechoslovak Chargé d'Affaires in Cyprus. He held not only a diplomatic post but was also one of the long-time secret collaborators of Czechoslovak intelligence (codenamed ABDUL). Grégr began to establish a network of informants and collaborators in Cyprus, some of whom had close ties to President Makarios (1960–1977) himself and his successor Spyros Kyprianou (1977–1988).¹³

It was originally planned that the Nicosia residency would be opened in 1974, following the Yom Kippur War, which triggered a renewed escalation of the political situation in the Middle East. However, the attempted overthrow of President Makarios in July 1974 and the subsequent Turkish intervention delayed the establishment of the residency for two years. The first resident assigned was Miroslav Chytrý (codename CHLÁDEK). The tasks of the intelligence service were aligned with Czechoslovakia's broader foreign policy interests in Cyprus, rooted in conceptual documents of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs from 1977. According to them, the attempts to establish two separate states in Cyprus in 1960s led the Cypriot government to seek allies, primarily among socialist and Third World countries. The 'Cyprus Issue' significantly impacted Greek-Turkish relations, thereby weakening of NATO's southeastern wing. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs noted that this situation, coupled with the Cypriot government's parallel interest in maintaining an independent and non-aligned Cyprus, created favourable conditions for the development of relations with socialist states, including Czechoslovakia. The Ministry stressed that in view of Czechoslovakia's long-standing support for Cypriot independence and the supply of arms, 'its position in Cyprus was somewhat exceptional and should be capitalized upon'.¹⁴ Consequently, the Czechoslovak approach after 1974 aimed to further expand relations with the

Republic of Cyprus in close cooperation with the Soviet Union, including in terms of support for the settlement of the Cyprus conflict in accordance with the UN resolutions.¹⁵

Although the Eastern Bloc states did call for an international conference to seek a future settlement of Cyprus with the help of the UN, in reality, they were comfortable with the division of the island. This was due to the further rapprochement between Moscow and Ankara, which was also backed by the embargo imposed by the United States on Turkey after its invasion of Cyprus. The Soviet Union sought to be more involved in the construction of industrial units and power stations in Turkey. The situation changed in the 1980s when Soviet-Turkish relations began to deteriorate. In 1981, the Panhellenic Socialist Movement (PASOK) won the national elections in Greece, which initially challenged Athen's membership in NATO and the EEC, opening up space for rapprochement with the socialist states of Eastern Europe and a greater understanding of Greek interests in the 'Cyprus Issue'. After the election of Mikhail Gorbachev as General Secretary of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union, the Eastern Bloc countries began to support again the idea of a major international conference to resolve the Cyprus conflict.¹⁶

The establishment of the residency in Cyprus was primarily aimed to encompass the acquisition of classified information related to Cyprus' domestic and foreign policies, shifts in relationships with the Eastern bloc, Greek-Turkish relations, as well as the intentions of the United States, Israel and other NATO countries in both Cyprus and the entire Middle East.¹⁷ The residency enjoyed particularly favourable operational conditions, enabling it to forge connections with high-ranking individuals within the Cypriot state apparatus. This was not solely due to some sympathizing with socialism and having respect for Czechoslovakia's long-standing backing of Cyprus, but also because of their unfavourable disposition towards Great Britain and the United States. The strong position of AKEL within the domestic political landscape, led by individuals who held positive attitudes to the ČSSR, also proved advantageous. This did not change even after the death of President Makarios in 1977. Moreover, Czechoslovak intelligence aimed to capitalize on the reality that certain Cypriots held British nationality and many pursued education or employment in the UK. This circumstance presented an opportunity to identify suitable individuals for potential posting to the United Kingdom or to other countries of interest to Czechoslovak intelligence. Further goals of the residency encompassed the handling of foreign nationals from NATO countries or Israel—whether they were military personnel, businesspeople, or members of the intelligence services. Considering Cyprus' geographical location within an area marked by conflicting interests of major NATO member states, the island served as an appropriate environment for the execution of active and influential measures with broad-reaching impact and efficiency. In this respect, the residency cooperated with other Czechoslovak residencies, especially the one in Athens, Ankara, Beirut, Cairo but also in Brussels.¹⁸ The agency environment was also favourable because of the little activity of the Cypriot counterintelligence. However, it was also beneficial to the other secret services.¹⁹ Czechoslovak intelligence also maintained contact with the intelligence agencies of other Eastern bloc countries, particularly the KGB, consulting on changes of the intelligence landscape and collaborating on joint actions related to the recruitment of collaborators or the execution of active measures. In the 1980s, Czechoslovak residents repeatedly met with their Soviet

counterparts but only scraps of concrete forms of cooperation have survived.²⁰ Information exchange also occurred with the Bulgarian intelligence, though significant cooperation only began in 1988. This was when two members of the Czechoslovak residency in Nicosia travelled to Sofia for an internship, paving the way for increased collaboration. Bulgarian intelligence during mutual conversations admitted that its activities in Cyprus primarily involved surveillance of British and US monitoring facilities on the island. It showed interest in partnering with Czechoslovak intelligence in this regard. Unlike the First Directorate, their focus was not predominantly on information activities and their active measures were directed at Turkey, highlighting its reluctance to resolve the 'Cyprus Issue' and its human rights violations.²¹

Agency network

The Czechoslovak intelligence network in Cyprus displayed remarkable diversity from the establishment of the residency in 1976 until the end of the Cold War. Miroslav Chytrý (CHLÁDEK), the first resident, skilfully leveraged pre-established contacts by Josef Grégr, particularly within the Cypriot civil service. By 1980, as Chytrý handed over his role to the new resident Jan Klimeš (BULDRA), the agency network comprised six cooperating individuals in the agent category and an additional three as 'confidential contacts'.²² In the subsequent year, the Nicosia residency reached its zenith with nine agents actively collaborating, including one who was recruited by a Cypriot citizen. However, as the late 1980s loomed, the ranks of collaborators began to thin, accompanied by a gradual decline in the quality of acquired information. Remarkably, given Cyprus' population at the time, which hovered around 700,000, this was a fairly large and high-quality agency network. However, a significant setback occurred following the defection of a veteran Czechoslovak intelligence officer, Vlastimil Ludvík (PANTŮČEK), in December 1988. Ludvík, who had overseen the Nicosia residency from the Prague headquarters, possessed sensitive information including the identities of its covert collaborators. Commencing in early 1989, due to the perceived risk of collaborator identities being compromised, the decision was made to gradually phase out cooperation with some of them. This pragmatic move eventually led to the stagnation of the agency's network.²³ The network itself can be classified into three main categories of collaborators. The first encompassed members and proponents of AKEL; the second involved former Cypriot students who had pursued their studies in Czechoslovakia; the third group consisted of Cypriot civil servants.

AKEL

The Progressive Party of the Working People (AKEL), established in 1941 as a continuation of the pre-war British-banned Communist Party of Cyprus, solidified its position as one of the most influential parties on the Cypriot political landscape following the establishment of the Republic of Cyprus. Boasting a membership of approximately 10,000, the party commanded around 30 % of the Cypriot electorate bolstered by its collaborative efforts with trade unions. Throughout the 1960s and 1970s, AKEL staunchly supported the non-aligned policies championed by President Makarios and his successor, Kyprianou.²⁴ AKEL maintained ties with the

Communist Party of Czechoslovakia (KSČ) from the 1950s onward. These contacts saw increased frequency after 1960, marked by regular exchanges of party delegations. AKEL even played a role in facilitating the acquisition of Czechoslovak arms in 1972.²⁵

The first collaborator associated with AKEL, was MP Dinos Constantinou. He was granted a scholarship to study in Czechoslovakia after completing high school. In 1958, he successfully graduated from the University of Economics in Prague and returned to Cyprus shortly afterwards. His initial interaction with a Czechoslovak intelligence officer on the island occurred in 1970 through Josef Grégr. Constantinou's trust in Grégr was further solidified due to his wife Marika, a Greek-origin emigrant had met during his Prague studies, who worked as a translator and secretary at the Czechoslovak embassy in Nicosia. The first resident Chytrý managed to rapidly foster the connection to the point that Constantinou was upgraded to the status of 'confidential contact' in 1977, code-named CANDIA. Constantinou's influential position granted him a broad spectrum of connections at the governmental level. Intelligence records highlight the value of details from discussion at the President's office and discreet parliamentary meetings that Constantinou had attended. However, the collaboration concluded in 1981, shortly after the supervision of Constantinou was transitioned to the new resident Jan Klimeš (BULDRA). Constantinou exhibited scepticism towards Klimeš and refrained from sharing information with him.²⁶

Another prominent AKEL member collaborating with the Nicosia residency was Christoforos Ioanides—Deputy Head of the International Department of the AKEL's Central Committee. Similar to Constantinou, Ioanides maintained very strong connections with Czechoslovakia. He had emigrated there in 1949 as a refugee from the Greek Civil War. In 1955, he gained admission to Charles University, specializing in archaeology, and successfully completed his studies in 1960. After the establishment of the Republic of Cyprus, Ioanides returned to his homeland and swiftly became involved in the AKEL. First contact with the residency was established in 1977 and in 1981, he was enlisted as a 'confidential contact', operating under the codename FAHRI. According to records, he cooperated with the intelligence service knowingly and willingly, based on his positive relationship with Czechoslovakia. In 1986, the AKEL designated him as its representative to the Prague-based magazine *Problems of Peace and Socialism*. The mutual cooperation did not end there, however, and he continued to be used to translate active measures, some of which he also edited. His engagement with Czechoslovak secret services lasted until the November 1989.²⁷

The final prominent figure in the Czechoslovak intelligence network in Cyprus associated with the AKEL was the journalist Stavros Angelides. Originally employed as a primary school teacher, he was detained by British authorities during the Cyprus Emergency due to his involvement in publishing anti-British materials. Following the proclamation of the Republic of Cyprus, Angelides fully immersed himself in journalism and began to work in *Haravgi*, the AKEL party's newspaper. His ties with Czechoslovakia trace back to 1961 when he visited ČSSR on the occasion of the Brno Fair. Throughout the 1960s, he served as a correspondent for the Czechoslovak Press Agency (ČTK) in Cyprus. Initial contact with Angelides was initiated in 1972 by Josef Grégr (ABDUL). In 1978, Angelides was enlisted to cooperate in the 'confidential contact' category, operating

under the codename AKRIS. He commenced contributions primarily in the areas of information intelligence and the execution of active measures, continuing this role until 1989.²⁸

Students

The second group of covert collaborators comprised former Cypriot students. This constituted a significant cluster, contributing several pivotal agents to the network. In the late 1950s, Czechoslovakia initiated the provision of economic and developmental aid to recently decolonized nations. This endeavour encompassed granting government scholarships for enrolment in Czechoslovak universities, designed to establish influence over emerging elites within these newly formed states. By 1963, the count of foreign students in Czechoslovakia exceeded 3,500, with a substantial portion hailing from the Third World countries. A special educational institution for foreign students, the University of 17th November, was even established, inspired by the Moscow University of the Friendship of Nations.²⁹ Selected recipients of foreign scholarship first underwent a one-year course in Czech or Slovak language before choosing from the array of Czechoslovak universities for their studies. The scholarship covered expenses tied to their academic pursuits and life within Czechoslovakia. Czechoslovak government scholarship also extended to Cyprus, with some awardees recommended by AKEL. In 1974, over 200 Cypriot students were studying in Czechoslovakia. Following the partition of Cyprus, this number declined, but by 1978 it hovered around 140. Two years later, 109 Cypriot students were enrolled in Czechoslovak universities, with 65 of being students selected by AKEL.³⁰ Czechoslovak secret services monitored Cypriot students during their stay in Czechoslovakia, identifying potential collaborators within them. A significant advantage of these student collaborators was their proficiency in Czech, significantly easing communication with intelligence personnel.

Among the most impactful student collaborators, Constantinos Karatsiolis emerges as a significant figure. Having completed his secondary education in Cyprus, he embarked on his journey as an editor at *Haravgi* newspaper in 1957. A few years later, he secured a scholarship to study in Czechoslovakia, where he distinguished himself with outstanding achievements at the Institute of Journalism and Education within the University of 17th November. His return to Cyprus in 1964 saw a continuation of his editorial role at the *Haravgi* newspaper, alongside assuming the mantle of a correspondent for the Czechoslovak Press Agency. Beyond journalism, Karatsiolis held a deep passion for history and literature, writing various poetry collections and novels under the pseudonym Kostas Grekos. However, 1968 saw him venture back to Czechoslovakia, this time to pursue doctoral studies at the University of 17th November. Concurrently, he served as the President of the Union of Cypriot Students in Czechoslovakia. His collaboration with Czechoslovak secret services was initiated during his doctoral tenure. Operating under the codename DÁMA, he provided the secret services with insights into the distinct attributes of Cypriot students in Czechoslovakia. Notably, he exposed the identity of an individual acting as an informant for the Cypriot Foreign Ministry. In 1970, Karatsiolis followed directives from Czechoslovak secret services by journeying to the headquarters of Radio Free Europe in Munich. Subsequently, he passed on the information about RFE's communication system to Czechoslovakia and Karel Jezdinský, one of the RFE editors.

He returned to Cyprus in 1970 as an established and reliable collaborator. Initially planning to work as a high school teacher, the intelligence service entrusted him with a pivotal role—to identify students keen on pursuing education at Western universities and harbouring aspirations of civil service employment upon their return to Cyprus. However, his ambition of securing a high school teaching position eventually faltered, leading to a temporary interruption in contact with Czechoslovak secret services. This break endured until 1977 when Karatsiolis, by then employed at the CBS radio and television company in Cyprus, re-established ties. In 1978, he was formally recruited as an agent, adopting the new codename KARAT.³¹ Three years later, the Nicosia residency had already come to regard him as one of the most valuable links within the agency's network.³²

Other vital connections within the agency network included Euripides Georgiades. After completing his secondary education and fulfilling his mandatory military service, he secured a scholarship to study medicine at Charles University. Following the successful completion of his studies in 1975, he was granted a two-year permanent residence permit in Czechoslovakia. This privilege was facilitated by his marriage to a fellow classmate of Czechoslovak nationality. Subsequently, Georgiades commenced work at a hospital in Orlová, situated in northern Moravia. His interaction with the Czechoslovak secret services commenced in 1977. He contributed information pertaining to the Greek exile community, which was notably present in the North Moravian region. Upon expressing his intent to return to Cyprus, the intelligence service initiated a collaboration with him prior to his departure under the designation of an agent, with the codename FIDAS. After his homecoming to Cyprus, he established a private practice. By 1981, the Nicosia residency already held him in high regard as one of its most beneficial covert collaborators. He gradually earned the designation of 'agent verbovčik', a distinctive category of collaborator tasked with recruiting individuals willing to cooperate with Czechoslovak intelligence.³³

However, it has not always been feasible to recruit former students who would ultimately prove to be an asset to the residency. Among these cases was Pavlos Flourentzos. Born in Famagusta, where he completed his high school education, he ventured to study in Czechoslovakia in 1966 on the recommendation of the AKEL. He pursued classical archaeology and art history at Charles University. Upon graduating, he returned to Famagusta alongside his wife—a Greek-origin emigrant he had met in Czechoslovakia. After the Turkish invasion, Flourentzos and his family lost all their belongings and were compelled to flee to the Greek part of the island. While his wife and daughter chose to return to Czechoslovakia immediately, Flourentzos managed to reunite with them a year later. In Czechoslovakia, he secured temporary residence until the situation in Cyprus stabilized. He subsequently joined the Archaeological Institute of the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences in Brno as a temporary staff member. His initial interaction with Czechoslovak secret services took place in 1975. Within a year, when he made the decision to return to Cyprus with his family, the intelligence service extended an offer of collaboration, which he accepted. Operating as an agent, he was enlisted under the codename ARCH. Before his departure, he underwent training in a concealed facility and received instruction in surveillance techniques, telephone interception, and correspondence scrutiny. Leveraging his education, linguistic proficiency, and occupational position, secret

services foresaw him as a potentially valuable source of information concerning foreigners from Western countries. His collaboration persisted until 1985, at which point the intelligence service decided to terminate it due to the consistently low quality of information being relayed by Flourentzos.³⁴

State administration

The final group of individuals collaborating with the Czechoslovak residency in Cyprus comprised civil servants, among whom the most valuable intelligence contacts emerged. The foremost significant figure who maintained consistent communication with Joseph Grégr was the secretary to Cypriot Presidents Makarios and Kyprianou Harris Vovides, who collaborated under the codename DOPAL. Unfortunately, the file concerning his collaboration remains classified and has yet to be released to the archive. Consequently, only fragments of other materials survive to offer insights into the extent of his collaboration. According to these fragments, he was enlisted to cooperate as a 'confidential contact' shortly after the end of the Yom Kippur War. During this conflict, he relayed information regarding activities by NATO countries in Cyprus, and he even participated in one of the active measures undertaken by Czechoslovak intelligence against Israel. He also furnished intelligence with materials originating from government and presidential office meetings.³⁵ Vovides, by virtue of his position, had close relations with President Makarios and apparently communicated with the intelligence service with his approval. In 1980 he was a member of President Kyprianou's delegation to Czechoslovakia. Intelligence planned a meeting with him during this visit to intensify cooperation, but no further information has been preserved.³⁶

One of the most invaluable members within the agency network of the Nicosia residency was Pavlos Stokkos, who was interned by the British in the mid-1950s. Following the establishment of the Republic of Cyprus, he embarked on a career in the police force. In 1963, he completed an FBI course in the United States and later received similar training in the UK. Before the partition of Cyprus, he served as the police commander in Larnaca. After the 1974 coup, he stood among the police officers who opposed Nicos Sampson, leading to his brief internment. Upon President Makarios' return to the island, Stokkos was rewarded for his loyalty by being summoned to Nicosia and promoted to the rank of general. The initial contact with the Cyprus residency occurred in 1977 through Miroslav Chytrý, who commenced the establishment of mutual trust between the two men. Part of this trust stemmed from Stokkos expressing a desire to acquire Czechoslovak pistols, which the resident willingly provided along with ammunition. Even when Stokkos faced temporary suspension from his post in 1978 in connection with the assassination of Egyptian Minister Yusuf Sibai in Cyprus,³⁷ the residency maintained communication. In fact, they began financially supporting him during his challenging life circumstances. This financial support likely played a pivotal role in his decision to collaborate, as by the year's end, he consented to cooperation and was designated as an agent under the codename BELIS. During the early years of their interaction, he had already furnished the residency with an analysis he had authored on the 1974 events, the 1976 Israeli police annual report, details on the Chief of Cypriot Intelligence's collaboration with the CIA, insights into the organizational structure of the Cypriot Intelligence Service, and information about the activities of EOKA B.³⁸ After his

recruitment, his primary task was to identify a young police officer for potential promotion to special police schools in the UK or the US, and subsequently facilitate their collaboration with Czechoslovak intelligence.³⁹

Stokkos' intelligence potential was significant, and this was one of the factors that led to his invitation to Czechoslovakia in 1981. He maintained connections with individuals within the Cypriot secret service, had an informant within the Cypriot police in British base Dhekelia, and possessed access to police records or vehicle registers. Additionally, he was in contact with individuals responsible for the security of embassies belonging to countries of priority interest for Czechoslovak intelligence, such as the United States, Great Britain, and Israel. However, the promising collaboration came to an abrupt halt in 1982 when news of Stokkos' collaboration with the Israeli secret service Mossad became public, leading to his immediate retirement. Following this revelation, on the direct orders of the Chief of Czechoslovak intelligence, Karel Sochor—incidentally the one who personally awarded Stokkos a medal during his visit to Prague—the collaboration was promptly terminated. This decision was made due to the loss of intelligence capabilities and the necessity to safeguard operational secrecy. Subsequently, intelligence was able to determine that Stokkos had seemingly been used by Mossad without engaging in direct cooperation with them. His removal from his position could have been linked to internal political struggle within the Ministry of the Interior. Alternatively, it cannot be ruled out that he was discredited based on requests from Western intelligence services due to his affiliations with Eastern Bloc, or possibly due to partial de-conspiracy efforts. Although Stokkos was later rehabilitated, the intelligence service exhibited no further interest in reinitiating their collaboration.⁴⁰

The last case of a civil service collaborator is Chrysostomos Sofianos. He pursued studies at the University of Athens in 1961. Successfully obtaining a UNESCO scholarship, he travelled to the United States, where he earned a doctorate from Ohio State University and subsequently served as a researcher there from 1973 to 1975. In 1976, President Makarios appointed him as the Minister of Education, a role he continued to hold when President Kyprianou came into power two years later. Notably, he visited Czechoslovakia in 1979 as part of a ministerial delegation. However, in 1980, he was relieved of his ministerial position. He subsequently founded the political party Pancyprrian Front for Renewal (PAME) and established the weekly newspaper *Kypriaki*. Miroslav Chytrý (CHLÁDEK) began encountering Sofianos at various social gatherings shortly after arriving in Cyprus. Over time, they cultivated a trustworthy relationship, which deepened when Sofianos sought Chytrý's assistance in facilitating his niece's education in Czechoslovakia. Additionally, Sofianos maintained a favourable rapport with the new resident, Klimeš, who provided him with a Czechoslovak-manufactured pistol for personal security at his request. According to intelligence records, Sofianos gradually grew accustomed to regular meetings and shared insights about Cypriot politics during these interactions. He also started featuring certain active measures by Czechoslovak intelligence in his weekly newspaper, *Kypriaki*, for which he received financial compensation. These funds served as a primary source of income for his newspaper. The official recruitment occurred in March 1982, during which Sofianos was openly informed of his collaboration with the Czechoslovak intelligence under the codename SUKRAN in the agent category. Subsequently, his role predominantly encompassed executing active measures and providing insights into Cypriot politics.

Nonetheless, the cooperation was relatively short-lived. Following the dissolution of his political party and the discontinuation of his weekly newspaper after the unsuccessful elections in 1983, Sofianos established a private consulting firm. He attributed his political downfall to AKEL and demanded a public apology from the party as a condition for continued cooperation. This request was deemed wholly unacceptable by the intelligence service. Moreover, as Sofianos exited politics, his intelligence capabilities diminished significantly. These factors, coupled with his reduced utility in his new role, led to the termination of cooperation in 1984.⁴¹

Reasons for cooperation, motives, and rewards

For most of the secret collaborators of the Czechoslovak residency in Cyprus, the motivation for cooperation was ideological affinity, which, however, took different forms for individuals. Among the collaborators from the circle of AKEL (CANDA, FAHRI), a positive attitude towards Czechoslovakia as a socialist country prevailed. Those who studied in Czechoslovakia and often came from modest family backgrounds, this factor was further accentuated that they had received a free university education, which helped them obtain relatively well-paid and socially respected employment upon their return to Cyprus. As a result, they felt indebted to Czechoslovakia in some way.

Some of the later collaborators from the circle of students had already been contacted by secret services (mostly counterintelligence) during their stay in Czechoslovakia. They underwent tests of reliability and potential for further intelligence use. Subsequently, they could be handed over to the Cyprus residency as cleared individuals, some of whom not only acted as informants but also continued to perform specific tasks on Czechoslovak territory. This was the case with KARAT and FIDAS. Another agent—ARCH—even underwent a short intelligence training to be better prepared for cooperation in Cyprus. Whenever possible, the intelligence services used the family background of collaborators or the fact that many of them had close relatives in Czechoslovakia to pressure, consolidate, and enforce cooperation. In FIDAS's case, it can be assumed that he was not allowed to take his advanced medical certification, which prevented him from staying longer in Czechoslovakia. Consequently, he had to return to Cyprus, where he immediately became involved in intelligence work.⁴² For ARCH, the secret services took advantage of the fact that his family had lost their property after the Turkish invasion. He received a financial reward of 2,000 CZK for basic moving expenses before returning to Cyprus.⁴³ KARAT received assistance from intelligence agency in his divorce from a Czechoslovak citizen whom he had married while still a student. When KARAT wanted to visit his children in Czechoslovakia in 1982, the intelligence agency offered to reimburse him for his stay.⁴⁴ Both of CANDA's children were studying in the Czechoslovakia. When his daughter encountered difficulties while studying medicine, the First Directorate offered to help him defer her exams extend her academic year.⁴⁵ Intelligence agency also managed to arrange studies in Czechoslovakia for SUKRAN's niece.⁴⁶ In SUKRAN case, it can also be said that, while ideological motives for cooperation were prevalent—his father was a long-time member of AKEL, SUKRAN considered socialism to be an appropriate establishment for Cyprus. It can be assumed that he also aimed to use the cooperation to rekindle his political career. The active measures he published in his weekly newspaper *Kypriaki* in exchange for intelligence corresponded

with his political programme, which advocated for a non-aligned and demilitarized Cyprus. This approach essentially created a partial election campaign for himself supported by intelligence funds.⁴⁷

A different motivation for cooperation can be traced in BELIS' case. He had a highly negative relationship with the British, claiming that they killed his father shortly after the war. He himself went through British internment in the mid-1950s. Despite repeatedly assuring the residency staff of his positive attitude towards Czechoslovakia, the intelligence service cited financial interest as his main motive for cooperation. BELIS had four daughters whom, according to Cypriot custom, he needed to provide for financially in order for them to marry well. In addition to smaller gifts in the form of a pistol or Czechoslovak glassware, he accepted financial rewards based on the quality and quantity of information he provided. He signed the acceptance under the codename Andreas Georghiou. During his stay in Prague, he also received 1,000 CYP, along with a medal, as an incentive for further cooperation. According to intelligence records, he was paid a total of 4,953 CYP and 3,500 USD, making him apparently the most highly rewarded member of the agency's network.⁴⁸ Apparently, he never learned that his first his initial meetings with the resident during which the money was handed over, were secretly recorded. These tapes could potentially be used for blackmail or compromise him in the future, if necessary.⁴⁹

Agent FIDAS was also compensated at a higher rate. However, in his case part of the remuneration was for expenses related to engaging potential collaborators. According to intelligence records, he received payments totalling 3,050 CYP and 600 USD between 1979 and 1988. Additionally, he was given 500 DM and over 10,000 CZK for expenses incurred during check-ups in Berlin and Czechoslovakia. In 1988, facing a more complicated personal financial situation, he requested a loan of 1,600 CYP from the intelligence service. Due to his long-term cooperation, the loan was approved. However, records indicate that he never repaid it, as the emigration of the PANTUČEK led to a freeze in cooperation.⁵⁰ Smaller sums were also provided to AKRIS for expenses, primarily related to translations of active measures. CANDIA and FAHRI received similar compensations.⁵¹ In the case of KARAT, the situation was an entirely different. His motivation for cooperation was, according to intelligence files, clearly ideological. Only on occasion did he accept small gifts in the form of cigarettes or alcohol. He adhered to a principle of refusing money for personal gain, only accepting it in exceptional cases connected with agency tasks. These instances included securing the cooperation of Cypriot student preparing to study in Belgium or a trip to Czechoslovakia to visit his children from his first marriage which also facilitated discussion for further cooperation.⁵²

Intelligence tasks and operations

One of the primary objectives of the residency in Cyprus was to gather confidential information about Cypriot politics, as well as the interests and activities of Western states and Israel on the island and the Middle East. The gathered intelligence not only contributed to the development of analyses on the Cyprus conflict but also extended to the broader Middle East region, which, after 1973, had once again become a focal point in the ongoing Cold War.⁵³ The quality of the obtained information varied over time,

depending on the intelligence capabilities of the collaborators and their willingness to share it. The intelligence agency highly valued its long-standing relationship with the Secretary to the President of Cyprus, Harris Vovidis (DOPAL). The intelligence received from him was generally regarded as of high quality, although existing records suggest that its usefulness declined after President Kyprianou took office. CANDAL also proved to be a valuable intelligence informant, providing 85 intelligence reports during the four years of cooperation, of which 58 were used for further intelligence purposes.⁵⁴ This relatively high number indicated their practical usability. KARAT, thanks to his work as a radio journalist, accessed behind-the-scenes information concerning foreign and domestic policies. The residency praised the content he transmitted. For instance, in 1981 alone, he shared 15 pieces of information, with 80 % of them being earmarked for further use.⁵⁵ However, BELIS can be considered the most vital informant of Czechoslovak intelligence in Cyprus. His contact within the Cyprus intelligence services furnished him with copies of investigations' results for the CIA. He was also informed about the latest trends and developments in intercommunity talks. Throughout their cooperation, BELIS forwarded 115 pieces of information and even proposed one active measure to the Czechoslovak residency.⁵⁶ Additionally, the First Directorate gleaned another type of information from BELIS—a description of the courses he had attended in the United States and the United Kingdom related to policing, including the names of fellow participants from the Cypriot police.⁵⁷

Among the primary targets for Czechoslovak residency in Cyprus were the British military bases of Dhekelia and Akrotiri. These bases' existence was secured by the Zurich-London agreements. Even after the establishment of the independent Republic of Cyprus, the bases remained a strategic military point for NATO countries and their operations in the Middle East. However, due to the events of 1974, the British contemplated abandoning the bases, partly due to the financial burden of maintaining them. Ultimately, this did not occur, largely due to the insistence of the United States, and the British bases survived beyond the end of the Cold War.⁵⁸ The residency aimed not only to monitor military activities within the bases but also to prevent their expansion for NATO purposes, or ideally, to entirely close them. The residency endeavoured to infiltrate the bases through civilian Cypriot employees facilitated by agents already collaborating with it (primarily FIDAS, and to some extent BELIS and KARAT).

Ultimately, Czechoslovak intelligence managed to achieve the goal of penetrating the British bases in two instances. In the first case, FIDAS succeeded in securing the cooperation of his childhood friend Eftimios Christou, who managed the officers' club at the Dhekelia base. After FIDAS's return from Czechoslovakia, he reconnected with Christou, and their friendship gradually deepened. This was partly due to FIDAS's involvement in successfully aiding Christou's seriously ill daughter. Intelligence records indicate that Christou appreciated the merits of the socialist system, and he held FIDAS's opinions in high regard. His negative sentiment towards the British also played a role in motivating his cooperation. Before Christou's official recruitment, he provided FIDAS with a map of the base, marked with various buildings that he had come across while cleaning the officers' club. He also handed over a list of military personnel within the base, complete with their telephone numbers. Additionally, he shared information about the base's defence protocols.⁵⁹ FIDAS recruited Christou in 1981 as an agent under the codename ERSU. This was in Czechoslovak intelligence jargon called a 'foreign-flag

recruitment' operation in which ERSU remained unaware that he was indirectly collaborating with the First Directorate. The cover used was that his gathered information would utilize to support one of the peace organizations that had long been advocating for the closure of British military bases on the island. During ERSU's recruitment, it was specified that his interactions would primarily focus on acquiring insights into British officers who frequented the club where he was employed. However, the primary objective of Czechoslovak intelligence was to utilize ERSU to introduce a listening device into the officers' club.⁶⁰ The exact location of the facility and other technical specifics were consulted in Moscow.⁶¹ Although ERSU agreed to the task and was prepared to execute it, the installation ultimately did not proceed due to the lack of suitable technical equipment possessed by the First Directorate.⁶² In 1984, ERSU was dismissed from the club for unspecified reasons. However, it has not been confirmed whether this was due to the discovery of his links to the residency. His subsequent employment at the Golden Beach Hotel in Larnaca ultimately proved to be impractical for intelligence purposes. As a result, the collaboration was definitively terminated by the headquarters' decision in 1988.⁶³

The second case was distinct. It involved a technician named Solon Kypridemos, who worked at the Akrotiri base (previously employed at Dhekelia). A chance encounter occurred between Kypridemos and resident Miroslav Chytrý (CHLÁDEK) during a cruise from Piraeus to Limassol in October 1978. Learning that Kypridemos was a British military base employee, Chytrý tried to establish a connection and learn more about him during the two-day cruise. In the subsequent months, CHLÁDEK assessed Kypridemos' political reliability and cultivated their friendship. This was facilitated through small tokens such as cigarettes or alcohol. CHLÁDEK evaluated Kypridemos, a member of the Democratic Party, as left leaning and harbouring anti-British sentiments, while maintaining a positive stance towards socialist countries. Their contact deepened relatively quickly, leading Kypridemos to share insights about British bases acquired not only from his personal experiences but also from discussions with fellow staff members. As early as December 1978, he had already provided telephone directories of the bases, revealing their general organizational structure. Furthermore, he conveyed details about the positioning of U-2 spy aircraft in Cyprus and shared observations regarding the security protocols, combat readiness arrangements, and nuclear attack contingency plans within the bases.⁶⁴ In 1980, he was officially recruited for cooperation as an agent, designated with the codename ARION. Given Kypridemos' notable freedom of movement within the Akrotiri base, intelligence officials aimed to glean insights from him regarding troop movements and potential combat readiness preparations. His tasks also included securing documents that could unveil NATO's military-strategic intentions in Cyprus and the Middle East.⁶⁵ However, the initial enthusiasm for cooperation soon waned. By the time of the 1986 assessment, intelligence had already noted a substantial decline in the quality of information shared. Consequently, a recommendation was made to permanently terminate the collaboration in 1988.⁶⁶

Another significant aspect of the Nicosia residency's operations was the formulation and execution of active measures. Taken from KGB terminology, this concept encompassed a range of disinformation and influence tactics, involving the dissemination of false information to harm adversaries and enhance one's own influence. Essentially, it represented a form of psychological or information warfare. Czechoslovak intelligence

began to excel in this arena as early as the 1960s, with its apparatus conducting numerous active measures globally. While most specific documentation related to disinformation campaigns has not survived, fragments can sometimes be found within secret collaborator records or residency files.⁶⁷ In the case of Nicosia, a few examples of these measures have endured, offering insight into their attributes, intentions, and the channels through which they were disseminated.

Among the initial active measures executed by the Nicosia residency was one code-named KÁDR. The objective was to apprise President Makarios of US plans that aimed to discredit him. These accusations involved circulating information that portrayed him as making decisions unilaterally, without consulting his advisors. The intention was to accuse Makarios of consolidating too much power and thereby sow discord among his associates. This active measure was built on partially true information sourced from the Brussels residency. The execution was facilitated through DOPAL, who maintained direct connections with the President. DOPAL conveyed this information to Makarios and informed the resident that a similar campaign was already underway in the *Simerini* newspaper. Consequently, in this instance, the residency was operating with partially accurate information which were intentionally exaggerated to harm relations between Makarios and the United States.⁶⁸

The active measure VALOR in the spring of 1977 had a similar purpose: to discredit both the United States and Great Britain. The core concept was to provide documentation of Turkey's arms purchases from Western countries, thus highlighting Ankara's involvement in military build-up. The primary supporting material for this measure consisted of photocopies of arms and military equipment purchase contracts signed in 1975 between Turkey and arms companies from the UK and the US. This essential documentation was acquired through a Czechoslovak intelligence agent operating within Western countries. However, the legend woven around this active measure indicated that the intelligence agency managed to secure these documents from the Turkish sector of Cyprus. The resident handed over the photocopies to DOPAL. To enhance the credibility of the legend, the resident visited the Turkish sector a day before, creating an appearance of alignment. DOPAL expressed enthusiasm for the documents and even inquired about sharing them with Greek secret services. The resident, ensuring the source's anonymity, consented to this request, and also agreed to have the information published in the Cypriot press.⁶⁹

Considerable attention was directed by the residency towards a series of active measures executed under the codename ASTRA. The objective was to counter the US military presence on British military bases in Cyprus, hindering their utilization by the Americans for operations within the Middle East. The foundational material for the inaugural active measure of this type, ASTRA I, consisted of intelligence gathered by the residency regarding the termination of Cypriot employees from British bases. This was supplemented with disinformation suggesting that these Cypriots were dismissed due to US pressure. Additionally, it was alleged that some of them would be replaced by US personnel, while others would be substituted by individuals associated with the former Iranian intelligence service SAVAK. This replacement group was said to also include Pakistanis and Afghans who had received specialized training in the US, preparing them for deployment as special forces in US-led operations in Iran or other Middle Eastern countries. The foundation for this disinformation campaign was propagated through

various channels within the intelligence network. AKRIS aimed to secure coverage in Cypriot press, while the reaction from unions regarding the discharged employees was to be coordinated by CANDA and FAHRI. Furthermore, DOPAL's role was to persuade President Kyprianou that the circulated information was authentic. Indeed, the active measure proved successful. In August 1980, multiple Cypriot and Greek newspapers published the information, with some warning about the transformation of British bases into American ones. This narrative raised concerns of a breach of the Zurich-London agreements, which pertained to Cyprus' sovereignty.⁷⁰ Subsequent active measures followed, retaining similar intentions yet manifesting in various forms. For instance, ASTRA II cantered on CANDA posing a question in the Cypriot Parliament regarding the misuse of British bases. ASTRA III, occurring in 1981, involved SUKRAN aiding in its publication within his newspaper. This instalment claimed that American special forces were stationed on British bases. Notably, due to the presence of Polish-speaking soldiers, it was alleged that the United States was preparing for a diversionary action on Polish territory. This insinuation coincided with a tense political situation in Poland at that time.⁷¹

The aforementioned examples of active measures constitute only a fraction of the disinformation campaigns executed by the Czechoslovak residency in Nicosia. The total count of these initiatives spanning from 1976 and 1989 could be estimated at over two dozen, with some being conducted in collaboration with the Soviet Union.⁷² Based on available records, AKRIS emerged as the most engaged figure in disseminating active measures. SUKRAN followed suit, publishing certain disinformation within his newspaper. Additionally, CANDA or BELIS were involved in a few cases. FAHRI also assumed a significant role, not only suggesting active measures to the residency, but also proposing a printing press for producing documents and leaflets in various languages.⁷³

Conclusion

The tradition of relations between the Republic of Cyprus and the Eastern Bloc countries dates back to the early 1960s when the island gained independence from Great Britain. Despite the division of Cyprus into Greek and Turkish parts in 1974, the interest of the Eastern European socialist countries in the island has not waned. The intervention of Turkish troops caused a split in the southeastern wing of NATO, which the Eastern Bloc sought to exploit to its advantage and strengthen its influence in Cyprus and the Eastern Mediterranean. This was facilitated, in no small part, with the help of the secret services.

One of the most active Eastern European secret services in Cyprus after 1974 was the Czechoslovak foreign intelligence. While other Eastern European intelligence agencies focused on the US and British radio and monitoring facilities (as was the case with Bulgaria), or on recruiting individuals for use in NATO countries (the Soviet Union), Czechoslovak intelligence primarily operated in Cyprus in the field of Human Intelligence (HUMINT). In 1976, it established its residency in Nicosia, which quickly managed to establish an extensive network of collaborators and informants in the Greek part of the island. They were mostly recruited from AKEL supporters, former Cypriot students in Czechoslovakia, and the Cypriot civil service. The intelligence agency capitalized on anti-Western sentiments on the island and the sympathy of part of its population towards socialism

to recruit individuals. Another advantage of the agency environment was that Cypriot counterintelligence was not very active against secret services of foreign states. Although Czechoslovak operatives were based in Nicosia, they also visited the Turkish part to gather information or conduct disinformation campaigns. While some members of the agency network cooperated with Czechoslovak intelligence out of ideological sympathies, others were paid or accepted gifts for their services. Some were coerced and pressured by intelligence. Motivation to cooperate also stemmed from efforts to maintain the independence of the Republic of Cyprus.

Czechoslovak intelligence, also thanks to its penetration into the highest levels of the Cypriot state administration, was able to obtain valuable information from its perspective on the development of Cypriot politics, Greek-Turkish relations, the evolution of the Cyprus conflict, and the situation in the Middle East. Some of this information was passed on by the residency to Czechoslovak intelligence and the KGB for further intelligence use. The main objectives of the residency were to weaken the influence of NATO states on the island, exacerbate their mutual disputes, and attempt to further tie the Republic of Cyprus to the Eastern Bloc. This was also pursued through active measures, dozens of which were implemented by the Czechoslovak intelligence with significant assistance from Cypriot collaborators. These measures were primarily aimed at discrediting Western countries, promoting the removal of British military bases, and deepening the disputes between Greeks and Turks. A special chapter in the activities of the First Directorate in Cyprus was the effort to penetrate British military bases. This succeeded in two instances when information about military activities was directly passed from civilian employees operating on the bases, along with efforts to instal a listening device in the Dhekelia base officers' club.

Although the Czechoslovak intelligence network, established over the years, collapsed in early 1989 due to the defection of a high-ranking intelligence officer, Vlastimil Ludvík, many of the activities of the Nicosia residency can be considered successful. The significant number of quality collaborators that Czechoslovak intelligence managed to recruit between 1974 and 1989 was due not only to the longstanding good relations between the two countries but also probably to the perception that cooperation with the intelligence service of a smaller socialist state was not necessarily seen as a threat to undermine Cypriot independence in some cases perhaps even strengthening it. Due to the lack of available Russian archival material, it remains difficult to assess whether the Soviet residency had more effective agency network than its Czechoslovak counterpart. Although, especially in the 1980s, the two agencies exchanged information and the residents met regularly, the available sources do not indicate that the KGB became more deeply involved in the operations of the Czechoslovak residency in Nicosia or somehow significantly instructed it. However, Czech archival records suggest that the Soviets also achieved remarkable results in Cyprus. So, research on this topic still remains open and holds further potential for exploring how Eastern European intelligence services intervened in the Cyprus conflict during the Cold War era.

Notes

- [1] Archiv bezpečnostních složek (ABS), f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 47156, program akce Belis, 20–24 September 1981, l. 50–52; *Ibid.*, A Belis—návrh na vyznamenání,

- 17 September 1981, l. 74; *Ibid.*, A Belis—záznam o průběhu a výsledcích jednání ve dnech 20–23. září 1981 v ČSSR, l. 53–55.
- [2] See e.g., R. Cormac, *Confronting the Colonies. British Intelligence and Counterinsurgency*, Hurst, London 2013, pp. 65–103; D. French, *Fighting EOKA. The British Counter-Insurgency Campaign on Cyprus, 1955–1959*, OUP, Oxford 2015; C. Walton, *Empire of Secrets. British Intelligence, the Cold War and the Twilight of Empire*, William Collins, London, 2014, pp. 304–315.
- [3] R. J. Aldrich, *The Hidden Hand. Britain, America and Cold War Secret Intelligence*, Overlook Press, Woodstock, 2002, pp. 567–580.
- [4] E. g. B. O'Malley, I. Craig, *The Cyprus Conspiracy. America, Espionage and the Turkish Invasion*, I. B. Tauris, London 1999; P. Dimitrakis, *Military Intelligence in Cyprus. From the Great War to Middle East Crises*, I. B. Tauris, London 2010; A. Constandinos, *America, Britain and the Cyprus Crisis of 1974. Calculated Conspiracy or Foreign Policy Failure?*, AuthorHouse, Milton Keynes 2009; C. Nicolet, *United States Policy towards Cyprus 1954–1974. Removing the Greek Turkish Bone of Contention*, Harassowitz, Mannheim 2001; L. Stern, *The Wrong Horse. The Politics of Intervention and the Failure of American Diplomacy*, Times Books, New York 1977.
- [5] A. Kadioğlu, E. Bezci, 'The Mystery of Intra-alliance Intelligence: Turkey's Covert Operations in the Cyprus conflict', *Middle Eastern Studies*, 56 (4), 2020, pp. 638–652.
- [6] The exception in this respect is: J. Koura, 'Czechoslovakia and the 'Cyprus Issue' in the years 1960–1974: Secret Arms Deals, Espionage, and the Cold War in the Middle East', *Middle Eastern Studies*, 57 (4), 2021, pp. 516–533; The Wilson Center recently published transcripts of a few documents from Bulgarian archives in this regard https://digitalarchive.wilsoncenter.org/search?search_api_fulltext=Cyprus+intelligence&items_per_page=10&sort_combine=created_DESC (25 February 2024). For general context see also: A. Christopher, V. Mitrokhin, *The Sword and the Shield. The Mitrokhin Archive and the Secret History of the KGB*, Basic Books, New York, 1999; A. Christopher, V. Mitrokhin, *The World Was Going our Way. The KGB and the Battle for the Third World*, Basic Books, New York, 2005.
- [7] Koura, op. cit.; J. Sakkas and N. Zhukova, 'The Soviet Union, Turkey and the Cyprus Problem, 1967–1974', *Les Cahiers Irice*, 1, 2013, pp. 123–135; A. Stergiou, 'Soviet Policy toward Cyprus', *Cyprus Review*, 19 (2), 2007, pp. 83–106.
- [8] For further details: Koura, op. cit.; J. Koura, *Διχοτομημένη νήσος Ψυχρός Πόλεμος και Κυπριακό την περίοδο 1960–1974*, Alexandria, Athens 2021.
- [9] *Ibid.*
- [10] P. Kaňák, J. Koura, 'In the Shadow of the KGB: Legacy of Czechoslovak Intelligence (1948–1989)', *International Journal of Intelligence and CounterIntelligence* 37 (2), 2024, pp. 450–481.
- [11] In its 'New Cold War History' series, the University of North Carolina Press has published a series of remarkable books based on archival material from former socialist countries that only became available to scholars after the fall of the Iron Curtain <https://uncpress.org/series/new-cold-war-history/> (25 February 2024).
- [12] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 11584, záznam o cestě na Kypr.
- [13] Koura, op. cit., pp. 525–526.
- [14] Archiv ministerstva zahraničních věcí (AMZV), TO-T, Kypr 1975–1979, Pro poradu kolegia ministra—zaměření a hlavní úkoly čs. zahraniční politiky vůči Kypru, č. j. 016.961/77–5, k. 1.
- [15] *Ibid.* Similarly, ABS, A2/7, i. j. 42, Základní dokumenty k realizaci bezpečnostní politiky strany po XV. Sjezdu Komunistické strany Československa, RMV ČSSR č. 42/1976, p. 114.
- [16] Stergiou, op. cit., pp. 99–100; Y. Nikita, D. Kuznetsov and L. Rustamova, 'Diplomatic Relations between Cyprus and the Soviet Union/Russia: From Cold War Games to Friendship and Comprehensive Cooperation', *Cyprus Review* 31 (3), 2019, pp.189–90.
- [17] ABS, A 2/5, návrh na zřízení residentur čs. rozvědky v Maroku, Tunisu a na Kypru, 21 March 1974.

- [18] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 11584, Kádrové rozšíření rezidentury Nikósie, 29 March 1979, l. 11–13.
- [19] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 81314, Schůzka s Felixem, 20 January 1989.
- [20] Ibid., Záznamy schůzek mezi československým a sovětským rezidentem na Kypru.
- [21] Ibid., Záznam v konzultativní stáži nového rezidenta v Nikósii u bulharských přátel ve dnech 5. 12.–10. 12. 1988.
- [22] An agent was a category of collaborator in Czechoslovak intelligence terminology, obtained for secret and knowledgeable cooperation. Agents were tasked with carrying out intelligence assignments, maintaining conspiratorial connections, and obeying the orders of supervising bodies. A confidential contact, due to their social status or personal characteristics, did not wish to work for intelligence. However, as part of cooperation, these collaborators voluntarily and knowingly shared classified information from their environment. Unlike an agent, a certain circle of individuals might have been aware that the confidential contact was interacting with a Czechoslovak citizen, and therefore such interactions had to be appropriately concealed. <https://ibadatelna.cz/cs/slovník> (16 September 2023).
- [23] D. Běloušek, 'Akce Pant. Příběh Vlastimila Ludvíka, posledního defektora komunistické rozvědky', *Sborník archivu bezpečnostních složek*, 6, 2008, pp. 243–260.
- [24] Stergiou, op. cit., p. 101. On the history of AKEL: Y. Katsourides, *The History of the Communist Party in Cyprus: Colonialism, Class and the Cypriot Left*, I. B. Tauris, London 2014.
- [25] Národní archiv Praha (NA), AÚV KSČ 100/3, Mezinárodní oddělení, sv. 107, a.j. 349, zpráva o cestě Papaioannou v Praze, 9 January 1950, l. 42; AMZV, TO-T, Kypr, 1970–1974, Materiály pro delegaci ÚV KSČ na 13. sjezd AKEL, č. j. 012021/74–5, 25 March 1974, k. 1.
- [26] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 46797, memorandum na agenturní typ Canda, 24 June 1977, l. 28–33; Ibid., Rozhodnutí o uložení svazku, 21 September 1982, l. 23–24.
- [27] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 47612.
- [28] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 47135.
- [29] See more: M. E. Holečková, *Příběh zapomenuté univerzity. Univerzita 17. listopadu (1961–1974) a její místo v československém vzdělávacím systému a společnosti*, Fontes, Praha 2019; C. Katsakioris, 'The Lumumba University in Moscow: Higher Education for a Soviet-Third World Alliance, 1960–91', *Journal of Global History*, 14 (2), 2019, pp. 281–300.
- [30] AMZV, TO-T, Kypr, 1970–1974, Materiály pro delegaci ÚV KSČ na 13. sjezd AKEL, č. j. 012021/74–5, 25 March 1974, p. 9, k. 1; AMZV, TO-T, Kypr 1975–1979, Podkladový materiál pro návštěvu ministra zahraničních věcí Rolandise v ČSSR, č. j. 053/1978, 16 August 1978, k. 1; NA, f. Gustav Husák, Kypr, Podklad pro jednání s prezidentem Kyperské republiky—hospodářské styky mezi ČSSR a Kyperskou republikou, 9 June 1980.
- [31] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 47070, AT Karat—návrh na získání ke spolupráci, 20 July 1978, l. 21.
- [32] Ibid., A Karat—plan prověrky, 2 March 1981, l. 19–22.
- [33] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 47006, A Fidas, návrh na využití v zahraničí, 11 August 1978, l. 35–40; Ibid., memorandum agenta, 30 September 1981, l. 73–113.
- [34] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 4677, Zpráva o získání ke spolupráci s československou rozvědkou, 9 April 1976, l. 30–35; Ibid., reg. č. 46577, Arch—ukončení spolupráce, 9 September 1985, l. 336–337.
- [35] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 11584, operativní dopis, 13 October 1977, l. 35–37; Koura, op. cit., p. 527.
- [36] Ibid., přijatá šifrovka, June 4, 1980, l. 140; NA, f. Gustav Husák, Kypr, Návštěva S. Kyprianou v Československu—seznam delegace, 6 June 1980.
- [37] For more details: Dimitrakis, op. cit., pp. 159–169.
- [38] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 47156, memorandum, 16 November 1978, l. 2–10; Ibid., A Belis—návrh na získání ke spolupráci, 23 November 1978, l. 11–22.
- [39] Ibid., Belis—poznatky ke spolupráci, 9 February 1982, l. 32.

- [40] Ibid., Belis—zhodnocení spolupráce, 2 August 1984, l. 62–64; Ibid., analýza případu Belis, 5 November 1982, l. 155–158.
- [41] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 47878, memorandum, 26 October 1981, l. 2–9; Ibid., A Sukran, zhodnocení spolupráce, 16 December 1983, l. 33–35; Ibid., A Sukran—uzavření spolupráce, 5 April 1984, l. 270–272.
- [42] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 47006, A Fidas—návrh na vyslání do zahraničí, 11 August 1978, l. 35–40.
- [43] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 4677, Zpráva o získání ke spolupráci s československou rozvědkou, 9 April 1976, l. 30–35.
- [44] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 47070, Karat—vyhodnocení spolupráce v r. 1982, 24 November 1982, l. 39–40.
- [45] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 46797, Canda – žádost o pomoc, 12 March 1977, l. 25.
- [46] ABS, f. Hlavní správa rozvědky, reg. č. 47878, návrh na získání agenta, 30 November 1981, l. 10–16.
- [47] Ibid.
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